

The content of microelements in the hair of healthy women of reproductive age of the Republic of Chuvashia

El contenido de microelementos en el cabello de mujeres sanas en edad reproductiva de la República de Chuvashia

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Received: 12/20/2022 Accepted: 03/19/2023 Published: 04/25/2023 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8001681>

Abstract

Background. Trace elements play a significant role in the regulation of the reproductive function of women and in many metabolic processes. In the studies of scientists, pathological changes in the microelement status of the population of various regions of Russia were found, associated with a violation of the consumption of chemical compounds, an increase in the concentration of heavy metals in water, air, food, etc.

Purpose of the study. Determine the content of trace elements in the hair of women of reproductive age living in the Republic of Chuvashia.

Materials and methods. The elemental composition of hair was studied in 25 conditionally healthy women

permanently residing in the Chuvash Republic. The analysis of 25 chemical elements was carried out in the laboratory of the ANO Center for Biotic Medicine (Moscow), accredited at the Federal Center for Sanitary and Epidemiological Supervision of the Ministry of Health and Social Development of the Russian Federation on the Optima 2000 DV spectrometers (Pekin-Elmer, USA) and Elan 9000 (Pekin-Elmer, USA) according to the standard technique of atomic emission and mass spectrometry with inductively coupled plasma in accordance with the methodological guidelines MUK 4.1.1482-03, 4.1.1482-03 (Ivanov S.I. et al., 2003).

Results. In women of reproductive age, a deficiency of selenium (9.3 times less than the reference value) and

chromium (10 times less than the reference value) was revealed. Revealed low levels of cobalt, cobalt, iodine, potassium.

Conclusion. Micronutrient deficiencies can affect reproductive function, lead to abnormalities during the gestational process, and affect the health status of newborns and young children.

The revealed changes in the hair composition are important for medical practitioners: this will allow them to correct various metabolic disorders in the body. This is especially important in order to prepare a woman for pregnancy.

Keywords: women of reproductive age, atomic emission spectrometry, mass spectrometry, microelements, macroelements.

Resumen

Fondo. Los oligoelementos juegan un papel importante en la regulación de la función reproductiva de las mujeres y en muchos procesos metabólicos. En los estudios de los científicos, se encontraron cambios patológicos en el estado de microelementos de la población de varias regiones de Rusia, asociados con una violación del consumo de compuestos químicos, un aumento en la concentración de metales pesados en agua, aire, alimentos, etc. .

Propósito del estudio. Determinar el contenido de oligoelementos en el cabello de mujeres en edad reproductiva que viven en la República de Chuvashia.

Materiales y métodos. La composición elemental del cabello se estudió en 25 mujeres condicionalmente sanas que residían permanentemente en la República de Chuvash. El análisis de 25 elementos químicos se llevó a cabo en el laboratorio del Centro de Medicina Biótica ANO (Moscú), acreditado en el Centro Federal de Supervisión Sanitaria y Epidemiológica del Ministerio de Salud y Desarrollo Social de la Federación Rusa en el Optima 2000 DV espectrómetros (Pekin-Elmer, EE. UU.) y Elan 9000 (Pekin-Elmer, EE. UU.) según la técnica estándar de emisión atómica y espectrometría de masas con plasma acoplado inductivamente de acuerdo con las directrices metodológicas MUK 4.1.1482-03, 4.1.1482- 03 (Ivanov S.I. et al., 2003).

Resultados. En mujeres en edad reproductiva se reveló una deficiencia de selenio (9,3 veces menos que el valor de referencia) y cromo (10 veces menos que el valor de referencia). Niveles bajos revelados de cobalto, cobalto, yodo, potasio.

Conclusión. Las deficiencias de micronutrientes pueden afectar la función reproductiva, provocar anomalías durante el proceso de gestación y afectar el estado de salud de los recién nacidos y los niños pequeños.

Introduction

Los cambios revelados en la composición del cabello son importantes para los médicos: esto les permitirá corregir varios trastornos metabólicos en el cuerpo. Esto es especialmente importante para preparar a una mujer para el embarazo.

Palabras clave: mujeres en edad reproductiva, espectrometría de emisión atómica, espectrometría de masas, microelementos, macroelementos.

It is widely recognized that micronutrients play an important role at many times in a woman's life. Insufficient reserves or consumption of trace elements can have adverse consequences for both the mother (hypertension, anemia, complications of childbirth) and the fetus (congenital malformations, premature birth, intrauterine growth retardation). Typically, the daily needs for minerals and trace elements are easily met by women who eat a balanced diet. This diet provides the RDA for all nutrients. Trace elements play a significant role in the regulation of the reproductive function of women and in many metabolic processes. Trace elements are necessary for antioxidant activity, as well as for functioning as cofactors for various antioxidant enzymes, in providing vital processes in the human body ^{1,2}.

Experience with micronutrients has been accumulated over the past few decades, and this knowledge has provided more information on the importance of micronutrient balance in the body. There is a growing awareness of the population, including among women of reproductive age, about the possible consequences of deficiency and about the toxicity of certain microelements.

These studies revealed a deterioration in the health status of the population, caused not only by nutritional disorders, but also by the impact of unfavorable environmental factors on the body ³. Pathological changes were found in the microelement status of the population of various regions of Russia, associated with a violation of the consumption of chemical compounds, an increase in the concentration of heavy metals in water, air, food, etc. ^{4,5,6}.

Studies of Russian and foreign scientists have shown that multiple imbalances of trace elements are more common. For example, high concentrations of lead, cadmium, mercury were found in residents of large industrial cities ⁷. At the same time, anthropogenically and naturally caused deficiencies of vital microelements were revealed ^{1,2,8,9,10,11}. Deviations in the content of iron, iodine, selenium, zinc were found among residents of large cities. The influence of microelementosis on the health status of the population of different age groups

is noted. According to the research results ², ecological and biogeochemical zones were identified on the territory of the Chuvash Republic with a significant imbalance in the elemental supply.

In addition, it was proved that in the reproductive period there remains an increased need for osteosynthetic, structural atomites (calcium, magnesium, fluorine, phosphorus, silicon), the need for endocrine (iodine, fluorine), biocatalytic (copper, zinc, magnesium, cobalt, manganese, silicon), elements involved in hematopoiesis (iron, arsenic, copper). Seasonal differences were identified: for example, in the winter months, a person needs calcium, potassium, magnesium, iron, manganese, chromium, silicon.

The name “microelements” was updated, they began to be called “atomites” ² or atoms of life. The classification of trace elements was built taking into account their quantitative content in the human body; by anatomical and physiological properties; by vital importance for the body; by the intensity of absorption in the gastrointestinal tract. According to the effect on the body, two main groups were distinguished: essential (iron, zinc, copper, manganese, cobalt), conditionally essential (nickel), toxic (lead, cadmium, mercury).

The study of the physical and chemical properties of elements, their distribution in the biosphere, the levels of content in soil, air, food, as well as the role for the functional state of the body made it possible to verify the diseases caused by the deficiency and excess of elements.

The results of clinical studies have convincingly shown that the deficiency of trace elements (Cu, Fe, I, Mn, Se, Zn) affects the body’s metabolism, in particular, lipid peroxidation changes, the metabolism of proteins, fats, carbohydrates is disrupted ^{1,2}. And only a balanced intake of elements with food, water in sufficient quantities is an important condition for maintaining the health of women of reproductive age. In this case, the formation of a depot of elements in various organs and tissues of a person is of decisive importance. In cases of nutritional deficiency or imbalance, it is necessary to prescribe the intake of macro- and microelements inside.

In addition, differences in the elemental status of residents of different regions of Russia and their relationship with the climatic, ecological and social conditions of life were noted ¹. Hyposelenosis was detected in 95% of the examined child population of the North-West region of Russia ³. When studying the elemental supply in the Chuvash Republic, a reduced content of calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, fluorine, iodine, cobalt, silicon, potassium, sodium in the blood of children compared with adults was noted ².

But, despite the previous studies, the study of the supply of women with microelements was not given due attention.

Methods

Purpose of the study

Determine the content of trace elements in the hair of women of reproductive age living in the Republic of Chuvashia.

The women underwent a thorough clinical and comprehensive laboratory examination, and also completed a questionnaire that included the items: age, place of residence, hair color, personal habits, occupation, BMI, exposure to adverse environmental factors and the use of medical procedures. Other exclusion criteria included a history of smoking, current pregnancy, acute and chronic infections, autoimmune, allergic, neoplastic and endocrine diseases, and other serious physical illness or injury, including surgery, within the past six months.

The elemental composition of hair was studied in 25 conditionally healthy women. The analysis of 25 chemical elements was carried out in the laboratory of the ANO Center for Biotic Medicine (Moscow), accredited at the Federal Center for Sanitary and Epidemiological Supervision of the Ministry of Health and Social Development of the Russian Federation on the Optima 2000 DV spectrometers (Pekin-Elmer, USA) and Elan 9000 (Pekin-Elmer, USA) according to the standard technique of atomic emission and mass spectrometry with inductively coupled plasma in accordance with the methodological guidelines MUK 4.1.1482-03, 4.1.1482-03 (Ivanov S.I. et al., 2003). At the same time, the parameters of the patients’ elementograms were compared with the average values of the content of these chemical elements in the hair (interquartile range) obtained during population studies in various regions of the Russian Federation (reference values) ¹. To assess the content of mercury, iodine, tin, boron vanadium, conditionally biological permissible levels (UBL) were used, which meant the levels of chemical elements that were empirically established based on long-term clinical observations that did not cause specific changes in human health ¹.

Our spectral analysis of hair in women of reproductive age ^{8,9} showed an imbalance in the elemental composition, in which increased levels of calcium, iron, magnesium, manganese prevailed in comparison with the reference values typical for women of the same age on average in the Russian Federation. The results of observations indicate that an increased content of calcium in the hair is considered as an indicator of an increased turnover of an element in the body, which subsequently leads to the development of its deficiency in the future. At the same time, there was a decrease in selenium in the hair of women of reproductive age.

The table shows the results of the analysis of the content of essential, conditionally essential and toxic elements in the hair of women of reproductive age in comparison with the reference values typical for the inhabitants of the Russian Federation and recommended as a physiological norm ¹ It is noted that hair is a biological object for the study of metabolic processes, since metabolic processes in them are slow.

The study of the composition of the hair reveals the ecological and physiological features of adaptation to the environment. It was proved ² that by analyzing the hair composition it is possible to identify ways of adaptation, as well as ways of correcting various metabolic disorders in the body.

Table 1. The content of chemical elements in the hair of healthy women of reproductive age in the Republic of Chuvashia, mg / kg

Element	M±m	Reference values q25-q75
Al (aluminum)	7,85 ± 0,99	9-23
As (arsenic)	0,131 ± 0,007	0-0,69
B (boron)	0,17 ± 0,328	0,1-3,5*
Be (beryllium)	0,01 ± 0,002	0 - 0,01
Ca (calcium)	771 ± 44,5	254 - 611
Cd (cadmium)	0,01 ± 0,003	0,03 - 0,18
Co (cobalt)	0,04 ± 0,002	0,02 - 0,11
Cr (chrome)	0,17 ± 0,007	0,26 - 0,7
Cu (copper)	9,62 ± 4,36	8 - 12
Fe (iron)	25,18 ± 4,36	13 - 27
Hg (mercury)	0,13 ± 0,024	0 - 1*
I (iodine)	1,03 ± 0,43	0,42 - 2,7*
K (potassium)	93,02 ± 72,6	53 - 663
Li (lithium)	0,007 ± 0,004	0 - 0,04
Mg (magnesium)	67,2 ± 8,5	18 - 56
Mn (manganese)	1,7 ± 0,13	0,32 - 0,93
Na (sodium)	560,23 ± 17,4	75 - 562
Ni (nickel)	0,53 ± 0,07	0,15 - 0,55
P (phosphorus)	134,4 ± 2,6	118 - 156
Pb (lead)	0,14 ± 0,07	0,76 - 2,73
Se (selenium)	0,26 ± 0,021	0,65 - 2,43
Si (silicon)	27,37 ± 1,26	10 - 27
Sn (tin)	0,09 ± 0,01	0,05 - 1,5*
V (vanadium)	0,03 ± 0,009	0,005 - 0,5*
Zn (zinc)	152 ± 4,3	94 - 183

Note: Me is the median, q25 is the lower quartile, q75 is the upper quartile;

* - conditionally permissible biological level

Zinc is essential for a number of enzymatic processes that ensure the biosynthesis of components of cell membranes, DNA, RNA. Recovery of zinc levels is possible with daily intake with water and food. A low zinc content in the body develops with enterocolitis, alcoholic hepati-

tis and leads to disturbances in taste, sensitivity, dermatitis, changes in the functional state of cellular immunity and the nervous system.

To maintain homeostasis, minerals are needed: calcium, magnesium, iron, zinc and others. Calcium is found in large amounts in bone tissue. The most important source of calcium is dairy products. There are age-related features of calcium absorption by the body. The daily calcium intake for women should be 1000 mg. Determination of calcium in hair is an important diagnostic step, since the determination of total and ionized calcium, which changes under different plasma conditions, does not show a true deficiency of the element.

According to the results of our spectral analysis of hair for women of reproductive age, an imbalance in the elemental composition in the content of essential and toxic substances was found. As it turned out, there were more women with increased levels of calcium, iron, magnesium, manganese in comparison with the reference values typical for women of the same age on average in the Russian Federation. At the same time, the content of calcium in the hair of women of reproductive age is increased: the median is 1.3 times higher than the upper limit of the norm.

Selenium is an element in antioxidant enzymes. The selenium content in women of reproductive age in Chuvashia is 2.5 times lower than the reference values.

The iodine index was noted at the level of the lower limit of the established physiological norm - 1.03 ± 0.43 mg / kg.

The zinc index is within the normal range and is 152 ± 4.3 mg / kg.

Trace elements affect a woman's reproductive health. Our studies have revealed the following changes in the hair of women of reproductive age from ecological and biogeochemical zones: deficiency of magnesium, magnesium, chromium, cadmium, magnesium, lead, increased content of silicon and molybdenum.

Copper is a trace element that provides oxidative processes, cellular respiration, the synthesis of female sex hormones and thyroxine, which affects the basal metabolism. Analysis of the elemental composition of hair in women of reproductive age revealed a low level of copper content. The median corresponds to the lower limit of the reference interval - 9.62 ± 4.36 mg / kg. We explain the low level of copper by the low content of the element in the environment. Probably, the copper content has seasonal characteristics, since cold exposure increases the need for this microelement ³.

Chromium deficiency leads to the development of type II diabetes mellitus associated with chronic chromium deficiency. In the study of chromium, the content was established at the level of 0.07 ± 0.007 mg / kg, which is 10 times less than the reference value. Chromium is

a vital element, participates in the maintenance of the cardiovascular system, regulates carbohydrate and fat metabolism.

When examining the level of toxin elements in women, no deviations were found, their content does not exceed the norm. The content of lead in hair was 0.14 ± 0.07 mg / kg, cadmium - 0.01 ± 0.013 mg / kg, mercury - 0.13 ± 0.024 mg / kg.

Our study revealed an imbalance in the provision of women of reproductive age in Chuvashia with essential and conditionally essential elements. A deficiency of selenium (2.5 times less than the reference value), chromium (1.5 times less than the reference value) was revealed. We found that the content of cobalt, magnesium, manganese, copper, zinc, iodine, potassium is within the reference values.

Micronutrient deficiencies can affect reproductive function, lead to abnormalities during the gestational process, and affect the health status of newborns and young children.

The revealed changes in the hair composition are important for medical practitioners: this will allow them to correct various metabolic disorders in the body. This is especially important in order to prepare a woman for pregnancy.

2019; 191(7):443. doi: 10.1007/s10661-019-7592-z.

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